

The effect of surface temperature for the scattering of D_2 ($v = 0, j = 0$)-Cu(111) system : A spherical polar TDDVR approach[†]

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Abstract : We have formulated a spherical polar Time Dependent Discrete Variable Representation (TDDVR) and perform four-dimensional (4D@2D) as well as six-dimensional (6D) quantum dynamics on a parametrically time and temperature dependent effective Hamiltonian for D_2 ($v = 0, j = 0$)-Cu(111) system. Such effective potential has been derived through a mean-field approach by considering weak correlation between molecular degrees of freedom (DOFs) and surface modes, where the initial state distribution of the surface modes were introduced through Bose-Einstein Probability (BEP) factor. We demonstrate the convergence of the theoretically calculated sticking probabilities employing 4D@2D quantum dynamics with increasing number of metal atoms as well as layers for rigid surface (RS) and surface at a particular temperature. It appears that the temperature dependent dissociation probabilities are exclusively dictated by those surface modes directed along Z-axis. The sticking probabilities obtained from 6D quantum dynamics are depicted as a function of initial kinetic energy (KE) of the diatom for RS and surface at 1000 K. Theoretically calculated sticking probabilities show the similar trend with the experimentally measured one.

Keywords : Spherical polar TDDVR, molecule-surface scattering, phonon modes, sticking probability.

I. Introduction

Both experimental measurements¹⁻⁵ and theoretical calculations⁶⁻²³ on the adsorption of diatomic molecule on metal surface have created huge interest to investigate the scattering and dissociation probability due to activated surface reaction as the paradigm of gas-surface reaction dynamics. Kroes and co-workers used DFT-GGA potential energy surface⁸ (PES) and calculated⁷ rovibrationally resolved transition probabilities (RRTP) for H_2 ($v = 1, j = 1$)-Cu(100) system, where Watts and Sitz² employed molecular beam techniques to detect the RRTP of scattered H_2 ($v' = 1, j'$) molecule. The analysis^{3,4} of experimentally measured adsorption data⁵ on the temperature dependent sticking probabilities for D_2 on Cu(111) surface show slight broadening on reaction probabilities at low and high initial KEs of the diatom over the temperature range, 120–1000 K.

The surface temperature could bring the effect of *sur-*

face mode vibrations and *electronic excitations* on the molecule-surface scattering processes, but there are only few attempts to investigate these phenomena from first principles : (a) The Hamiltonians were derived by considering a single oscillator¹⁰⁻¹³ for H_2 -Cu(1nn) systems or few oscillators¹⁴ for H_2 -Si(100) system; (b) The role of lattice motion¹⁵ and its' reconstruction for the dissociation of CH_4 on Ni(111) surface at various temperatures had been studied¹⁶⁻¹⁸, where the activation energy for the reaction changes with the surface oscillator coordinate, Q ; (c) The formulation of effective Hamiltonian by incorporating oscillators¹⁹⁻²⁴ originating from the atoms of multiple layers of a particular metal surface [Cu(1nn), $n = 0, 1$] with its specific plane (1nn).

In order to account the interaction between the molecular DOFs and the surface modes accurately at a specific surface temperature, the model Hamiltonians were modified by including a single¹⁰⁻¹³ or few¹⁴ oscillator(s)

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or by lattice reconstruction^{16–18} and the corresponding time-dependent Schrödinger equation (TDSE) had been solved by multi-configuration approach, but those approaches incorporate the surface temperature through an *ad hoc* manner because the temperature of a system can only be defined by an ensemble of particles. In case of many oscillators, a fully correlated description between the surface modes and the diatomic DOFs leading to a Multi-Configuration Time Dependent Hartree (MCTDH) approach, but such an approach could be computationally intractable for so many DOFs. On the contrary, if we assume a weak correlation between molecular DOFs and surface modes due to huge mass difference between the incoming diatom and the metal atoms, and thereby, incorporate those effect into molecular DOFs through a mean-field treatment. In order to incorporate the surface temperature accurately, it is necessary to consider all the oscillators (up to Debye frequency) arising from the multiple layers of the metal surface and their all possible quantum state until the convergence of calculated sticking probabilities achieved.

We have used^{21–24} the effective Hamiltonian obtained by employing a mean-field approach to include the effect of phonon modes by considering Bose-Einstein probability (BEP) factor for the initial state distribution of those modes. The “direct”^{23,24} solution of Linearly Forced Harmonic Oscillator (LFHO) is involved to derive the time and temperature dependent effective Hamiltonian. On the other hand, it is necessary to show the convergence of the sticking probabilities with respect to the number of atoms and layers of the surface and the importance

of perpendicular (Z) modes over the parallel (X and Y) ones within 4D⊗2D quantum dynamical calculation to demonstrate the numerical validity of the solution of TDSE. Finally, we perform 6D quantum dynamics and calculate converged sticking probability of the diatom. In order to perform those numerical calculations, we have implemented a spherical polar TDDVR to carry out the quantum dynamics and calculate sticking probabilities of the diatom on the rigid surface and surface at 1000 K.

II. The Embedded Diatomics in Molecules (EDIM) potential for D₂-Cu(111) interaction

In this article, we perform quantum dynamics on the ground adiabatic (Born-Oppenheimer) analytical potential energy surface (PES) constructed by using EDIM method (see Appendix A) as proposed by Truong *et al.*³⁹ by using DFT-GGA data⁴⁰ and compared the potential values with the available results^{40–42}. The barrier heights (E_b) and their locations (r_b , Z_b) on the EDIM-fit PES are presented in Table 1 in case of D₂-Cu(111) system. Fig. 1 shows the PES ($V_0(r, Z)$) for dissociation from : (a) *ttb* site with barrier height 0.80 eV and the corresponding

Table 1. The barrier heights (E_b) and their locations (r_b and Z_b) are given for D₂ dissociating with its molecular axis kept parallel to the Cu(111) surface. The numbers in the parenthesis are the results of Díaz *et al.*⁴²

Impact site	Dissociation to	E_b (eV)	r_b (Å)	Z_b (Å)
Top	Bridge	0.80 (0.89)	1.32 (1.40)	1.48 (1.39)
Bridge	Hollow	0.38 (0.63)	1.08 (1.03)	1.30 (1.17)

Fig. 1. The contour plot of EDIM-fit ground adiabatic PES ($V_0(r, Z)$) for H₂/D₂, (a) interacting on top site and dissociating to bridge site, (b) interacting on bridge site and dissociating to hollow site of Cu(111) surface.

X, Y, Δ, t) is the first derivative of the molecule-surface $V_k^{(1)}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t)$. $V_k^{(1)}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t)$ where $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, p\}$ and $V_k^{(1)}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t) = \frac{1}{\omega_k} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(l - \zeta_k^p)^2} \omega_k^l V_k^{(l)}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t)$.

$$(8) \quad V_{\text{eff}}^{\text{nh}}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2) = \sum_k \frac{1}{\omega_k} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(l - \zeta_k^p)^2} \omega_k^l V_k^{(l)}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2)$$

the initial states of those surface modes at temperature, T_2 : with diston and by considering the BE distribution for assuming only linear coupling terms of phonon modes The effective potential is derived (see Appendix B) by wavefunction.

system within Harteve product approximation of the total $\phi, X, Y, \Delta, t, T_2$) is for the phonon coupling for same Cu(111) system, where the effective potential, $V_{\text{eff}}^{\text{nh}}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2)$ (see Section II) for D_{2h} diston, respectively. $V_0(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2)$ is the rigid sur- where μ and M are the reduced and total mass of the

$$(7) \quad V_{\text{tot}}^{\text{nh}}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2) = V_0(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2) + V_{\text{eff}}^{\text{nh}}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2)$$

and

$$(6) \quad V_0(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2) = \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{v}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\phi}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\theta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\phi}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\phi}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\theta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\phi}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\phi}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\theta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\phi}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2$$

$$\hat{H}_0(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2) = \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{v}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\phi}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\theta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu \dot{\phi}^2 + \frac{1}{2} M \dot{\Delta}^2$$

(2) $V_{\text{eff}}^{\text{nh}}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2) + \hat{H}_0(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2) = \hat{H}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2)$ Hamiltonian $\hat{H}(v, \theta, \phi, \Delta, t, T_2)$ following form of time and temperature dependent effective Such product-type wavefunction [eq. (1)] leads to the fol- (4) $\langle \alpha | U(t, T_2) | \beta \rangle = \langle \alpha | U(t, T_2) | \beta \rangle$ evolution operator $U(t, T_2)$ as given below :

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where the amplitudes $\alpha_{\{n\}}(t)$ arise from a set of initial states $\{v_0\}$, to all possible final states $\{v\}$, due to the

$$(3) \quad \Phi_{\text{ph}}(\{v\}, t) = \sum_{\{n\}} \alpha_{\{n\}}(t) | \{v\} \rangle$$

The wavefunction $\Phi_{\text{ph}}(\{v\}, t)$ for the phonon modes is expressed (see Appendix B) :

$$(2) \quad \Phi_{\text{ph}}(\{v\}, t) = \sum_{i_1, \dots, i_p} c_{i_1, \dots, i_p} \prod_{l=1}^p \psi_{i_l}(X_l, t)$$

Section III(C) : basis functions $[\psi_{i_k}(X_k, t)]$ for various modes (q) (see Dependent Discrete Variable Representation (DDVR) molecular DOFs is expanded in terms of products of time The wavefunction $[\Psi(\{X_k\}, t)] = \Psi(\{X_k\}, t)$ for $\Psi(\{X_k\}, t) = \Phi_{\text{ph}}(\{v\}, t) \Phi_{\text{mol}}(\{X_k\}, t)$.

the wavefunction is considered as :

metal surface. With this assumption, the product form of due to huge mass difference between the diston and the subsystems are neglected by assuming weak interaction cross correlation among the configurations of different $\{X_k\}$ are fully correlated with each other, but the turn states, where the configurations within a subsystem possible configurations arising from their various diston- $\{X_k\}$ and phonon modes $\{Q\}$ have the access to all is such that the time evolution of the molecular DOFs initial state distribution. The formulation of this approach sidering Bose-Einstein (BE) probability factors for their phonon modes at non-zero temperature by con- plying a mean-field approach to include the effect of We have formulated an effective Hamiltonian by em-

III.A. Formulation of effective Hamiltonian

III. Theoretical Development

previous theoretical⁴¹ and experimental⁴³ results.

are endothermic in nature, which is also supported by the (0.89 eV). Our EDIM fitted PES both for the and the site site shows reasonable agreement with the SRP-DFT data approach to DFT. Moreover, our calculated E_b data for the have calculated the $E_b = 0.63$ eV using a SRP ap- estimated in the range 0.46–0.22 eV, but Diaz et al.⁴² matches well with the earlier results of Hammer et al.⁴¹ minimum barrier height in case of the with EDIM-fit the exit channel at $v_b = 1.08$ Å and $\Delta_b = 1.30$ Å. The site with lowest barrier height 0.38 eV and it is located in barrier geometry at $v_b = 1.32$ Å, $\Delta_b = 1.48$ Å; (d) the

interaction potential, $z_k(T_s) = \exp(-\hbar\omega_k/k_B T_s)$ is the partition function and ω_k s are the surface mode frequencies. While deriving eq. (8), the expression of transition probability for the phonon modes from the set $\{n\} \rightarrow \{m\}$ is considered from the “direct”^{23,24} solution of linearly forced harmonic oscillator (LFHO). The expression of energy transfer²⁴ from molecule to solid or vice versa, (ΔE_{ph}) is given by :

$$\Delta E_{ph} = \sum_k \frac{\hbar\omega_k \rho_k}{3N-6} \sum_{q=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-z_k^q)}, \quad (9)$$

where ρ_k is the excitation strength and $3N-6$ is the number of normal modes originating from the surface atoms (N).

IIIB. The TDDVR methodology in spherical polar coordinates

The TDDVR is a well established²⁵⁻³⁶ molecular dynamics quantum simulation method on systems with many DOFs. Though the detailed formulations of the different versions of TDDVR approach are presented successively elsewhere²⁵⁻³⁶, those implementations are carried out either in Cartesian or normal mode coordinates. At present, we employ a spherical polar TDDVR to investigate the dynamical phenomena originating due to molecule-surface interaction, where the molecular Hamiltonian is expressed in spherical polar coordinates. The prime technical point of TDDVR dynamics is the movement of basis functions in few specific DOFs (r , X , Y and Z) by using “classical” equations of motion.

The adiabatic representation of TDSE for the diatom-surface interaction Hamiltonian [see eq. (6)] on a single BO surface is :

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi(\{X_k\}, t) = \hat{H}(\{X_k\}, t, T_s) \Psi(\{X_k\}, t), \quad (10)$$

where

$$\int \Psi^\dagger(\{X_k\}, t) \Psi(\{X_k\}, t) \prod_{k=1}^p dX_k = 1, \quad (11)$$

at any time t and $\{X_k\} \equiv r, \theta, \phi, X, Y, Z$. The wavefunction $[\Psi(\{X_k\}, t)]$ for many DOFs (p) is expanded in terms of products of either DVR $[\{\psi_{i_k}(X_k)\}]$ or TDDVR $[\{\psi_{i_l}(X_l, t)\}]$ basis functions for the various modes,

$$\Psi(\{X_k\}, t) =$$

$$\sum_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_p} c_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_p}(t) \prod_{l=1}^q \psi_{i_l}(X_l, t) \prod_{k=q}^p \psi_{i_k}(X_k). \quad (12)$$

In case of r, X, Y, Z coordinates, we employ the TDDVR basis functions constituted by using the harmonic oscillator eigenfunctions :

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{i_l}(X_l, t) &= \phi(X_l, t) \sum_{n=0}^{N_l} \xi_n^*(x_{i_l}) \xi_n(x_l) \\ \phi(X_l, t) &= \pi^{1/4} \exp\left(\frac{i}{\hbar} \{P_{X_l^c}(t)[X_l - X_l^c(t)]\}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where

$$\xi_n(x_l) = \left(\frac{2ImA_l}{\pi\hbar}\right)^{1/4} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n!2^n\sqrt{\pi}}} \exp\left(-\frac{x_l^2}{2}\right) H_n(x_l), \quad (14a)$$

$$x_{i_l} = \sqrt{\frac{2ImA_l}{\hbar}} (X_{i_l}(t) - X_l^c(t)), \quad (14b)$$

A TDDVR grid-point, X_{i_l} , is determined by eq. (14b) using the root, x_{i_l} , of $(N_l + 1)$ -th Hermite polynomial, $H_{N_l+1}(x_l)$. Since the roots (x_{i_l} s) of the polynomial are fixed values, the positions of the TDDVR grid-points (X_{i_l} s) will change as a function of time due to the time-dependent variables, $X_l^c(t)$,

$$X_{i_l}(t) = X_l^c(t) + \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2ImA_l}} x_{i_l}. \quad (15)$$

On the other hand, for θ and ϕ coordinates, the DVR basis functions are used in terms of particle in a sphere eigenfunctions :

$$\psi_{i_k}(X_k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N_k} \chi_n^*(X_{i_k}) \chi_n(X_k), \quad (16)$$

where the primitive basis for θ coordinate in the range 0 to π are given by :

$$\chi_n(X_\theta) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sin(nX_\theta), \quad (17)$$

and those basis for the ϕ coordinate in the range 0 to 2π

are defined as :

$$\chi_n(X_\phi) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi}} \sin\left(\frac{nX_\phi}{2}\right). \quad (18)$$

The DVR grid points, X_{i_θ} and X_{i_ϕ} are the roots of the particle in a sphere basis functions.

The TDDVR/DVR basis functions, ψ_{i_k} s, as defined in eq. (13)/eq. (16) for the k -th mode constitute an unnormalized orthogonal set,

$$\int dX_k \psi_{i_k}^*(X_k, t) \psi_{i'_k}(X_k, t) = \delta_{i_k i'_k} A_{i_k i'_k}, \quad (19)$$

where A_k is the normalization factor.

When the molecule-surface interaction Hamiltonian [see eq. (6)] and the TDDVR representation of wavefunction [eqs. (12)-(18)] are substituted into the TDSE [eq. (10)], the classical path picture appears naturally along with the quantum equation of motion. The compact form of TDDVR matrix equation for quantum motion can be derived by employing time-dependent variational principle⁴⁴ as given below :

$$i\hbar \dot{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{H}^t\mathbf{C} \quad (20)$$

and the matrix equation under a similarity transformation takes the following convenient form

$$i\hbar \dot{\mathbf{D}}(t) = \mathbf{A}^{-1/2} \mathbf{H}^t \mathbf{A}^{-1/2} \mathbf{D}, \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{A}^{1/2} \mathbf{C}$. The explicit expression of the differential equation for an amplitude, $d_{i_X i_Y i_Z i_\theta i_\phi}$, is

$$\begin{aligned} i\hbar \dot{d}_{i_X i_Y i_Z i_\theta i_\phi} &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \sum_l \dot{P}_{X_l^c} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{ImA_l}} \bar{G}_{i_l i_l} \right\} d_{i_X i_Y i_Z i_\theta i_\phi} \\ &+ \left\{ \sum_l \frac{m_l (X_l^c)^2}{2} \right\} d_{i_X i_Y i_Z i_\theta i_\phi} \\ &- \sum_l \left\{ \frac{\hbar ImA_l}{2m_l} \sum_{i'_X i'_Y i'_Z i'_\theta i'_\phi} \{ \bar{F}_{i'_l i'_l} \} d_{i'_X i'_Y i'_Z i'_\theta i'_\phi} \right. \\ &\left. \prod_{l' \neq l}^q \delta_{i_{l'} i'_{l'}} \delta_{i_{\theta l'} i'_{\theta l'}} \delta_{i_{\phi l'} i'_{\phi l'}} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} \frac{1}{X_{i_r}^2} \left[\frac{4}{\pi(N_\theta + 1)} \sum_{n=1}^{N_\theta} \sin(nX_{i_\theta}) n^2 \sin(nX_{i'_\theta}) \right] \prod_{l' \neq l}^q \delta_{i_{l'} i'_{l'}} \delta_{i_{\phi l'} i'_{\phi l'}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &- \frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} \frac{1}{X_{i_r}^2} \left(\frac{1 \cos^2 X_{i_\theta}}{4 \sin^2 X_{i_\theta}} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \prod_{l' \neq l}^q \delta_{i_{l'} i'_{l'}} \delta_{i_{\theta l'} i'_{\theta l'}} \delta_{i_{\phi l'} i'_{\phi l'}} \\ &+ \frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} \frac{1}{X_{i_r}^2 \sin^2 X_{i_\theta}} \left[\frac{1}{\pi(N_\phi + 1)} \sum_{n=1}^{N_\phi} \sin\left(\frac{n}{2} X_{i_\phi}\right) \right. \\ &\left. n^2 \sin\left(\frac{n}{2} X_{i'_\phi}\right) \right] \prod_{l' \neq l}^q \delta_{i_{l'} i'_{l'}} \delta_{i_{\theta l'} i'_{\theta l'}} \\ &+ V_0(X_{i_X}, X_{i_Y}, X_{i_Z}, X_{i_r}, X_{i_\theta}, X_{i_\phi}) d_{i_X i_Y i_Z i_\theta i_\phi} \\ &+ V_{eff}^{ph}(X_{i_X}, X_{i_Y}, X_{i_Z}, X_{i_r}, X_{i_\theta}, X_{i_\phi}, t, T_S) d_{i_X i_Y i_Z i_\theta i_\phi}. \quad (22) \end{aligned}$$

The explicit expression of the component matrices (\mathbf{D} , \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{F}) of TDDVR equation of motion are presented in Appendix C. The contribution of different modes on a time-dependent amplitude ($\dot{d}_{i_X i_Y i_Z i_\theta i_\phi}$) can be evaluated independently, i.e., \mathbf{F}_1 matrix couple grid points or basis functions of the l -th mode only. This feature allows *parallelization of the algorithm*³³, reduces computational cost remarkably³³⁻³⁶ and paves the possibility to pursue relatively large dimensional calculations. On the other hand, the classical path equations for the l -th mode, those appear along with the quantum equation of motion, can be written as :

$$\dot{X}_l^c(t) = \frac{P_{X_l^c}(t)}{m_l}, \quad (23)$$

$$\dot{P}_{X_l^c}(t) = - \left. \frac{dV(\{X_l\})}{dX_l} \right|_{X_l(t)=X_l^c(t)} + X_l^F(t), \quad (24)$$

where m_l is either the reduced (μ) or the total (M) mass of the diatom and $X_l^F(t)$ quantum force.

III C. Initialization, propagation and projection

We perform both four-dimensional (4D \otimes 2D) and six-dimensional (6D) quantum calculations on an effective Hamiltonian [see eq. (6)] that defines molecule-surface interaction including the effect of phonon modes. In those calculations, the initial wavefunction could be represented as :

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(r, \theta, \phi, X, Y, Z, t_0) &= \frac{1}{r} g_u(r) Y_{j m_j}(\theta, \phi) \\ \Phi_{GWP}(X, t_0) \Phi_{GWP}(Y, t_0) \Phi_{GWP}(Z, t_0), \quad (25) \end{aligned}$$

where r is the bond distance, the polar angles θ and ϕ specify the orientation of the diatomic molecule, $g_v(r)$ is the Morse eigenfunction and Y_{jm_j} is a spherical harmonics. The GWP ($\Phi_{GWP}(Z, t_0)$) for the Z coordinate represents the translational wavefunction for the COM of the incoming diatom with a initial momentum, $p_0(= \hbar k_0)$, where the corresponding wavevector (k_0) appears in its' plane wave component as given below :

$$\Phi_{GWP}(Z, t_0) = \left[2\pi\Delta_Z^2 \left(1 + \frac{\hbar^2 t_0^2}{4M^2\Delta_Z^4} \right) \right] \exp \left(-\frac{(Z - Z_{foc} - \hbar k_0 t_0 / M)^2}{4\Delta_Z^4 - 2i\hbar t_0 / M} - ik_0 Z \right). \quad (26)$$

The wavepacket is initially centred around Z_0 , where t_0 is the time at which the GWP is focused around Z_{foc} with a width $\Delta Z \left(= \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\hbar / ImA_Z} \right)$. On the contrary, as the initial wavefunction should be spread uniformly over the X - Y plane, we introduce $\Phi_{GWP}(X, t_0)$ and $\Phi_{GWP}(Y, t_0)$ for the X and Y coordinates without any specific momentum component. Thus, the initial wavefunction [eq. (25)] can be expressed in terms of TDDVR basis functions as given below :

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(r, \theta, \phi, X, Y, Z, t_0) &= \sum_{IJKLMN} C_{IJKLMN}(t_0) \psi_I(r) \\ &\times \psi_J(\theta) \psi_K(\phi) \psi_L(X) \psi_M(Y) \psi_N(Z) \\ &= \frac{1}{r} g_v(r) \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sin \theta}} Y_{jm_j}(\theta, \phi) \Phi_{GWP}(X, t_0) \\ &\times \Phi_{GWP}(Y, t_0) \Phi_{GWP}(Z, t_0). \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

If we define the amplitude of the wavefunction only at the TDDVR grid points, the function takes the following form due to orthogonality relationship of the basis functions [see eq. (19)] known at the grid points :

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(r_I, \theta_J, \phi_K, X_L, Y_M, Z_N, t_0) &= \frac{C_{IJKLMN}(t_0)}{ImA} A_{II}^r A_{JJ}^\theta A_{KK}^\phi A_{LL}^X A_{MM}^Y A_{NN}^Z \\ &= \frac{1}{r_I} g_v(r_I) \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sin \theta_J}} Y_{jm_j}(\theta_J, \phi_K) \Phi_{GWP}(X_L, t_0) \\ &\times \Phi_{GWP}(Y_M, t_0) \Phi_{GWP}(Z_N, t_0), \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

which in turn gives the following expression for the initial amplitude of the wavefunction :

$$\begin{aligned} d_{IJKMLN}(t_0) &= ImA \frac{\frac{1}{r_I} g_v(r_I) \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sin \theta_J}} Y_{jm_j}(\theta_J, \phi_K)}{\sqrt{A_{II}^r A_{JJ}^\theta A_{KK}^\phi A_{LL}^X A_{MM}^Y A_{NN}^Z}} \\ &\times \Phi_{GWP}(X_L, t_0) \Phi_{GWP}(Y_M, t_0) \\ &\Phi_{GWP}(Z_N, t_0). \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

$$\text{where } ImA = \left(\frac{\hbar}{2} \right) (ImA_r ImA_X ImA_Y ImA_Z)^{\frac{1}{4}}.$$

When the scattered wave function is far away from the interaction region, the energy resolved elastic/inelastic state to state transition probabilities can be calculated as the ratio of the outgoing ($C_{k_{out}, v'j'm_j}^+$) and the incoming (C_{k_{in}, vjm_j}^+) fluxes :

$$P_{v'j'm_j}^{vjm_j}(E) = \frac{\frac{k_{out}}{M} |C_{k_{out}, v'j'm_j}^-|^2}{\frac{k_{out}}{M} |C_{k_{in}, vjm_j}^-|^2}, \quad (30)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} C_{k_{out}, v'j'm_j}^+ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} ImA \\ &\times \sum_{IJKLMN} \left(\frac{d_{IJKLMN}}{\sqrt{A_{II}^r A_{JJ}^\theta A_{KK}^\phi A_{LL}^X A_{MM}^Y A_{NN}^Z}} \right) \\ &\times \frac{1}{r_I} g_v^*(r_I) \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sin \theta_J}} Y_{j'm_j}^*(\theta_J, \phi_K) \exp(-ik_{out} Z_N) \\ &\times \exp\left\{ \frac{i}{\hbar} [P_{Z_c}(Z_N - Z_c)] \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (31a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{k_{in}, vjm_j}^+ &= \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \right)^{1/4} \\ &ImA \sqrt{\Delta_Z} \exp[i(k_{in} - k_0)Z_c - \Delta_Z^2 (k_{in} - k_0)^2] \\ &\frac{1}{r_I} g_v(r_I) \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sin \theta_J}} Y_{jm_j}(\theta_J, \phi_K) \\ &\times \frac{1}{\sqrt{A_{II}^r A_{JJ}^\theta A_{KK}^\phi A_{LL}^X A_{MM}^Y}} \\ &\times \Phi_{GWP}(X, t_0) \Phi_{GWP}(Y, t_0). \end{aligned} \quad (31b)$$

and k_{in} and k_{out} indicate the incoming and outgoing wave vectors, respectively. The sticking probability ($P_{stick}(E)$) can be defined as :

$$P_{stick}(E) = 1 - \sum_{\nu'j'm_j'} P_{\nu j m_j}^{\nu'j'm_j'}(E). \quad (32)$$

IV. Results and discussion

The workability of our theoretical approach based on mean-field approximation, which incorporate the effect of surface modes on the molecular DOFs, is explored by calculating sticking probabilities of the diatom (D_2) with increasing number of metal atoms in different layers of the Cu(111) surface for rigid and surface at temperature, T, where the solution of TDSE is obtained by employing a spherical polar TDDVR. Table 2 shows the Cu(111) surface is constructed by taking various layers (1st, 2nd

Set	Total number of atoms	Number of atoms in 1st layer	Number of atoms in 2nd layer	Number of atoms in 3rd layer
I	27	11	10	6
II	49	19	18	12
III	65	29	20	16
IV	89	35	30	24
V	134	49	36	49

and 3rd) with different total number of surface atoms (27, 49, 65, 89 and 134). As it has been predicted^{14,15} that the perpendicular (Z) surface modes are the effective ones for the temperature dependent reaction probabilities, we demonstrate the contribution of perpendicular (Z) and all surface modes on the calculated sticking probabilities employing our approach at a given surface temperature, T.

We have carried out 4D \otimes 2D and 6D quantum dynamics on a 6D effective Hamiltonian derived by incorporating BEP factor for the initial state distribution of the phonon modes to include the effect of surface temperature. Since a huge amount of computation is necessary to demonstrate the convergence of reaction probabilities with respect to the number of atoms and layers of the surface and the contribution of perpendicular (Z) and all surface modes, we perform majority of the calculations within 4D \otimes 2D quantum dynamics but finally, reaction probabili-

ties are calculated by 6D quantum dynamics as a function of initial KE of the diatom for rigid surface (RS) and surface at 1000 K.

When the surface is made up with increasing number of metal atoms placed in three different layers, Figs. 2 and 3 depict the convergence profiles for the sticking probabilities of the D_2 molecule on the surface as a func-

Fig. 2. Calculated sticking probability ($P_{stick}(E)$) using 4D \otimes 2D quantum dynamics considering RS in case of D_2 ($\nu = 0, j = 0$)-Cu(111) system as a function of initial collision energy for 27 (black circle), 49 (red square), 65 (blue triangle up), 89 (magenta cross) or 134 (green star) atoms, respectively, placed in 3 layers.

Fig. 3. Calculated sticking probability ($P_{stick}(E)$) at 1000 K using 4D \otimes 2D quantum dynamics in case of D_2 ($\nu = 0, j = 0$)-Cu(111) system as a function of initial collision energy for 27 (black circle), 49 (red square), 65 (blue triangle up), 89 (magenta cross) or 134 (green star) atoms, respectively, placed in 3 layers. The effective Hamiltonian has been formulated by using BEP factor.

tion of initial kinetic energy of the diatom for the RS and the surface at 1000 K, respectively. Both for RS and surface at temperature 1000 K, the sticking probability reaches the convergence with 49 number of Cu atoms. On the other hand, Figs. 4 and 5 demonstrate the conver-

Fig. 4. Calculated sticking probability ($P_{stick}(E)$) using 4D@2D quantum dynamics considering RS in case of D_2 ($v = 0, j = 0$)-Cu(111) system as a function of initial collision energy including only one (black circle), two (red square) or three (blue triangle up) layers, respectively, for set V atom distribution.

Fig. 5. Calculated sticking probability ($P_{stick}(E)$) using 4D@2D quantum dynamics at 1000 K in case of D_2 ($v = 0, j = 0$)-Cu(111) system as a function of initial collision energy including only one (black circle), two (red square) or three (blue triangle up) layers, respectively, for set V atom distribution. The effective Hamiltonian has been formulated by using BEP factor.

gence profile of sticking probabilities of the D_2 molecule on the surface by increasing the number of layers of the metal surface for the RS and surface at 1000 K, respectively. When one (first), two (first and second) and three (first, second and third) layers are considered in our calculation to explore the convergence of reaction probabilities with increasing number of layers, the number of metal atoms incorporated are 35, 65 and 89, respectively. Both these figures clearly show that the convergences of the sticking probabilities are achieved only when two layers are included in the calculations.

In Fig. 6, we demonstrate the importance of the per-

Fig. 6. Calculated sticking probability ($P_{stick}(E)$) at 1000 K using 4D@2D quantum dynamics in case of D_2 ($v = 0, j = 0$)-Cu(111) system as a function of initial collision energy. The dynamics have been carried out by including all phonon modes (red square), the phonon modes along Z vibrations (blue triangle up) and for RS (black circle) for three layers considering set V atom distribution. The effective Hamiltonian has been formulated by using BEP factor.

pendicular (Z) surface modes on the calculated sticking probabilities (see set V in Table 2). The reaction probabilities due to the surface at 1000 K including both the parallel (X and Y) and perpendicular (Z) modes originating from three (1st, 2nd and 3rd) layers exactly match with those probabilities obtained by including only the perpendicular (Z) surface modes at 1000 K involving three (1st, 2nd and 3rd) layers. Such probabilities depict not only the sole contribution of perpendicular mode over others but also the broadening (increasing and decreasing at low and high collisional energy, respectively) at a given surface temperature with respect to the RS one.

Finally, the 6D computed sticking probabilities are displayed in Fig. 7 for the collision of D_2 on Cu(111) surface for RS and surface at 1000 K. Though calculated reaction probabilities by employing 4D@2D show only slight broadening at low and high initial KE of the diatom, it becomes prominent in the 6D computed profile. In other words, our theoretically calculated results find the similar trend with the experimental⁴ one, i.e., with increasing surface temperature, reaction probabilities increase and decrease at low and high collisional energies, respectively.

V. Summary

We have implemented a spherical polar TDDVR to perform 4D@2D and 6D quantum dynamics on an effective Hamiltonian for D_2 ($v = 0, j = 0$)-Cu(111) system at

Fig. 7. Calculated sticking probability ($P_{stick}(E)$) using 6D quantum dynamics considering BEP factor in case of $D_2(\nu = 0, j = 0)$ -Cu(111) system as a function of initial collision energy, where experimental results are taken from Ref. [4].

different surface temperature, where the effective potentials are derived by considering a product type wavefunction (mean-field) between molecular DOFs and surface modes. While constructing the wavefunction for each subsystem, all possible configurations are included and those configurations are correlated with each other but the configurations of different subsystems are not by considering that the interactions between molecular DOFs and phonons are enough weak due to huge mass difference. The interaction of phonon modes with the molecular DOFs are included through LFHO. Since we wish to carry out the dynamics at different surface temperatures, the approach incorporates the effect of phonon modes by employing Bose-Einstein probability (BEP) factor for the initial state distribution of the surface modes.

The theoretical validity of our mean-field approach has been investigated by performing the following calculations : (a) The convergence of calculated sticking probabilities with increasing number of metal atoms and layers of the Cu(111) surface by considering RS and the surface at a particular temperature, T; (b) The effect of perpendicular (Z) or all surface modes on the temperature dependent sticking probabilities. Such calculations show that the perpendicular (Z) modes are the only contributing ones over other (X and Y) surface modes for the broadening of sticking probabilities at a particular temperature as predicted previously^{13,15} and depict exact agreement with those probabilities obtained by including both parallel (X and Y) and perpendicular (Z) surface modes. Moreover, the trend of broadening on the stick-

ing probabilities is same with the experimentally⁴ measured one. In conclusion, the mean-field approach employed while developing present theory can essentially capture most of the features predicted by earlier theories^{13,15} and experimental⁴ measurement, where the methodology based on spherical polar TDDVR can reproduce the sticking profile enough accurately while solving the TDSE and establish the numerical validity.

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Appendix A : Embedded Diatomics In Molecules (EDIM) methodology

The embedded diatomics in molecules method (EDIM) is an extension of the embedded atom method (EAM) to molecules using the diatomics in molecules (DIM) approach⁴⁵. In the DIM method, the two adiabatic surfaces are obtained from :

$$\mathbf{T}^\dagger \mathbf{S}^{-1/2} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{S}^{-1/2} \mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} W_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & W_{22} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where \mathbf{T} diagonalizes $\mathbf{S}^{-1/2} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{S}^{-1/2}$, and

$$\mathbf{S}^{-1/2} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{6}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2} - \sqrt{6}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A2})$$

The elements of the \mathbf{H} matrix are given by³⁹ :

$$H_{11} = 4(Q_{ab} + Q_{aM} + Q_{bM} + J_{ab}) - 2(J_{aM} + J_{bM}), \quad (\text{A3a})$$

$$H_{22} = 4(Q_{ab} + Q_{aM} + Q_{bM} + J_{aM} + J_{bM}) - 2J_{ab}, \quad (\text{A3b})$$

and

$$H_{12} = H_{21} = -2(Q_{ab} + Q_{aM} + Q_{bM} + J_{ab} + J_{aM} + J_{bM}), \quad (\text{A3c})$$

where the indices a and b represent the gas phase atoms and M represents the metal. In our case, the dynamics is carried out on the lower adiabatic curve W_{11} for which we get :

$$W_{11} = \frac{1}{6}(H_{11} + H_{22} + H_{12}) - \frac{1}{6}\sqrt{\frac{H_{11}^2 + H_{22}^2 - H_{11}H_{22} + 2H_{12}}{\times(2H_{12} + H_{11} + H_{22})}} \quad (\text{A4})$$

The quantities, Q and J are Coulomb and exchange integrals for the diatomic fragments and are constructed with the interaction energies using the equations :

$$Q_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(E_{ij}^s + E_{ij}^t), \quad (\text{A5a})$$

$$J_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(E_{ij}^s - E_{ij}^t), \quad (\text{A5b})$$

where s and t denote the singlet and triplet bonding and antibonding energies. For the gas phase atoms a and b , the interaction energies are given by Morse and anti-Morse functions, i.e.,

$$E_{ab}^s = D_{ab}(1 - \exp(-\alpha_{ab}(R_{ab} - R_{eq}^{ab})))^2 - D_{ab}, \quad (\text{A6a})$$

$$E_{ab}^t = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1 - S_{ab}}{1 + S_{ab}} (D_{ab}(1 + \exp(-\alpha_{ab} \times (R_{ab} - R_{eq}^{eq})))^2 - D_{ab}), \quad (\text{A6b})$$

where D_{ab} is the dissociation energy, R_{ab} is the separation between the atoms and $(1 - S_{ab})/(1 + S_{ab})$ is the Sato factor. The singlet and triplet interactions between the gas phase atom a and the Metal M are given by the EAM method, i.e.,

$$E_{aM}^s = F_a(\bar{\varrho}_a) + \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_M} \phi_{\alpha\alpha}(R_{a\alpha}), \quad (\text{A7a})$$

$$E_{aM}^t = -F_a(\bar{\varrho}_a) + \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_M} \phi_{\alpha\alpha}(R_{a\alpha}), \quad (\text{A7b})$$

where $R_{a\alpha}(=|r_a - r_{\alpha}|)$ is the distance between the gas phase atom a and each of the atoms in the metal α . The first term in eq. (A7) is the embedding energy :

$$F_a(\bar{\varrho}_a) = \frac{\delta_4 \bar{\varrho}_a}{1 + \frac{\delta_3 \bar{\varrho}_a}{1 + \frac{\delta_2 \bar{\varrho}_a}{1 + \delta_1 \bar{\varrho}_a}}}, \quad (\text{A8})$$

where δ_i s are parameters⁴⁵ fitted to properties of the molecule-surface interaction.

The second [in eq. (A7)] is the screened Coulomb pair potential :

$$\phi_{a\alpha}(R_{a\alpha}) = Z_a(R_{a\alpha})Z_{\alpha}(R_{a\alpha})/R_{a\alpha}, \quad (\text{A9a})$$

$$Z_q(R_{a\alpha}) = Z_0^q(1 + \beta_q R_{a\alpha}^{\nu_q})\exp(-\gamma_q R_{a\alpha}), \quad (\text{A9b})$$

where $Z_q(R_{a\alpha})$ is the effective nuclear charge of the q atom at distance $R_{a\alpha}$. Z_0^q , β_q , γ_q and ν_q are the parameters of the potential and $q = \alpha$ (for metal), a or b (for gas phase atom).

$\bar{\varrho}_a$ is the electron density from the metal atoms at the position of atom a , i.e.,

$$\bar{\varrho}_a = \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_M} \varrho_{\alpha}(R_{a\alpha}), \quad (\text{A10})$$

where the atomic density, ϱ_{α} , is given by contributions from outer shell 4s-electrons and 3d electrons, i.e.,

$$\varrho_{\alpha}(R_{a\alpha}) = n_s \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_M} \varrho_{\alpha,s}(R_{a\alpha}) + n_d \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_M} \varrho_{\alpha,d}(R_{a\alpha}). \quad (\text{A11})$$

n_s and n_d are the number of valence s and d electrons and $\varrho_{\alpha,s}(R_{a\alpha})$ and $\varrho_{\alpha,d}(R_{a\alpha})$ are the densities associated with an s and d electron, respectively.

The electron density $\varrho_{\alpha,p}(R_{a\alpha})$ from atom α at position $R_{a\alpha}$ can be expressed as :

$$\varrho_{\alpha}(R_{a\alpha}) = (1/4\pi) \left[\sum_i C_i \mathfrak{R}_i(R_{a\alpha}) \right], \quad p \in (s, d) \quad (\text{A12})$$

where

$$\mathfrak{R}_i(R_{a\alpha}) = \frac{(2\zeta_i)^{n_i+1/2}}{\sqrt{(2n_i)!}} R_{a\alpha}^{n_i-1} \exp(-\zeta_i R_{a\alpha}). \quad (\text{A13})$$

The coefficients C_i s, the exponent ζ_i and n_i are obtained from Clementi-Roetti tables⁴⁶.

Appendix B : The molecule phonon interaction

Since the detailed formulation of effective potential for molecule phonon interaction is carried out elsewhere²⁴, only a brief outline is presented here for completeness. The excitation of phonon modes to different quantum states arise due to the anharmonic terms of the interaction

potential (V_I) between gas molecule and surface atoms, where such potential on expansion in terms of phonon coordinates (Q_k s) is given by :

$$V_I = V_I^0 + \sum_k V_k^{(1)} Q_k + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{kl} V_{kl}^{(2)} Q_k Q_l + \dots, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $V_I^{(0)}$ is the interaction potential with the lattice atoms at the equilibrium geometry. The first derivative ($V_k^{(1)}$) and second derivative ($V_{kl}^{(2)}$) in eq. (A1) are the cause for phonon excitation due to diatom-surface collision. The normal modes (Q_k s) are expressed in terms of boson creation (b_k^\dagger)/annihilation (b_k) operators such as $Q_k = A_k(b_k^\dagger + b_k)$ and $A_k = \sqrt{\hbar/2\omega_k}$. The $(3N - 6)$ number of non-zero frequencies (ω_k s) are obtained by diagonalizing the force constant (Hessian) matrix of the solid.

Introducing the time dependent amplitude $\alpha_{\{n\}}(t)$ for a given phonon state $\{n\}$, we obtain the effective potential as :

$$\langle V \rangle_{\{n\}}(t) = \sum_{\{n'\}} \sum_{\{n''\}} \alpha_{\{n'\}}^*(t) \alpha_{\{n''\}}(t) \langle \{n'\} | V_I | \{n''\} \rangle, \quad (\text{A2})$$

where such potential implicitly depends on the initial state $\{n_0\}$. The amplitudes $\alpha_{\{n\}}(t)$ arise from a given initial state $\{n_0\}$ as given below :

$$\alpha_{\{n\}}(t) = \langle \{n\} | U(t, t_0) | \{n_0\} \rangle, \quad (\text{A3})$$

where $U(t, t_0)$ is the evolution operator for the phonon states due to the molecule-surface interaction potential. In order to include a distribution of states rather than a specific initial state, we define an average potential by :

$$\langle V \rangle(t, T_s) = \sum_{\{n\}} p_{\{n_0\}} \langle V \rangle_{\{n_0\}}(t). \quad (\text{A4})$$

The quantity, $p_{n_k^0}$, can be expressed by BEP factor :

$$\begin{aligned} p_{n_k^0} &\propto \frac{1}{\exp(n_k^0 \hbar \omega_k \beta) - 1} \\ &= z_k^{n_k^0} (1 - z_k^{n_k^0})^{-1} \\ &= z_k^{n_k^0} + z_k^{2n_k^0} + z_k^{3n_k^0} + z_k^{4n_k^0} + \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5})$$

where the Boltzmann constant, k_B appears in the partition function, $z_k = \exp(-\beta \hbar \omega_k)$ with $\beta = 1/k_B T_s$. The so called low temperature expansion of the BEP factor [$z_k^{n_k^0} (1 - z_k^{n_k^0})^{-1}$] is used because it is equally valid both at

low ($z_k^{n_k^0} \ll 1$) as well as high ($z_k^{n_k^0} \approx 1$) temperature limits with sufficient number of terms, but the high temperature expansion of the BEP factor is valid subject to the numerical magnitude of the argument of the exponential in partition function.

Considering the BEP factor [eq. (A5)] for the initial state distribution of the phonon modes and inserting eq. (A1) in eq. (A4), we obtain the following form of the effective potential :

$$\begin{aligned} \langle V \rangle(t, T_s) &= \sum_k \sum_{n_k^0} \sum_{n_k} p_{n_k^0} A_k V_k^{(1)} [n_k^{1/2} \alpha_{n_{k-1}}^{*(k)}(t) \\ &\times F_k^- + (n_k + 1)^{1/2} F_k^+ \alpha_{n_{k+1}}^{*(k)}(t)] \alpha_{n_k^{(k)}}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A6})$$

where $F_k^- = \exp(-i\omega_k t)$ and $F_k^+ = (F_k^-)^*$ are the interaction representation of the phonon states and $V_k^{(1)} = \partial V_I / \partial Q_k|_{eq}$ is the first derivative with respect to the normal mode coordinate evaluated at the equilibrium position of the lattice atoms.

While deriving eq. (A6), we have furthermore used :

$$\alpha_{\{n\}}(t) = \prod_{k=1}^M \alpha_{n_k}^{(k)}(t), \quad (\text{A7})$$

and $\sum_{n_k} |\alpha_{n_k}^{(k)}(t)|^2 = 1$, where $\alpha_{n_k}^{(k)}(t)$ is the amplitude for the n_k -th quantum state in mode k .

It is important to note that the exact solution for the Linearly Forced Harmonic Oscillator (LFHO) is given by³⁸ :

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{n_{k+1}}^{*(k)}(t) &= \exp\left(-i\beta k - \frac{1}{2}\rho_k\right) \\ &[(n_k + 1)! n_k^0!]^{1/2} (-i\alpha_k^-)^{n_k - n_k^0 + 1} f(\rho_k, n_k + 1), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A8})$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{n_k}^{(k)}(t) &= \exp\left(i\beta k - \frac{1}{2}\rho_k\right) \\ &\times [n_k! n_k^0!]^{1/2} (i\alpha_k^+)^{n_k - n_k^0} f(\rho_k, n_k), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A9})$$

where

$$\rho_k = \alpha_k^+ \alpha_k^-, \quad (\text{A10})$$

$$\alpha_k^\pm = -\frac{A_k}{\hbar} \int_{t_0}^t dt' V_k^{(1)} \exp[\pm i\omega_k t'], \quad (\text{A11})$$

with

$$\beta_k = \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_0}^t dt' V_k^{(1)} \{ \exp[i\omega_k t'] \alpha_k^-(t') - \exp[-i\omega_k t'] \alpha_k^+(t') \}. \quad (\text{A12})$$

The $f(\rho_k, n_k)$ is defined by

$$f(\rho_k, n_k) = \frac{1}{n_k!} L_{n_k}^{n_k - n_k^0}(\rho_k), \quad n_k \geq n_k^0, \quad (\text{A13})$$

and

$$f(\rho_k, n_k) = \frac{1}{n_k^0!} (-\rho_k)^{n_k^0 - n_k} L_{n_k}^{n_k^0 - n_k}(\rho_k), \quad n_k < n_k^0. \quad (\text{A14})$$

where $L_{n_k}^{n_k^0 - n_k}$ is the Laguerre-polynomial.

When the modified Bessel-function of the first kind is employed, the expression in eq. (A6) is simplified to :

$$V_{eff}^{ph}(t) = \langle V \rangle(t, T_s) = \sum_k \omega_k^{-1} \epsilon_k(t) \sum_{q=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-z_k^q)}, \quad (\text{A15})$$

with $\epsilon_k(t) = V_k^{(1)}(t) \int_{t_0}^t dt' V_k^{(1)}(t') \sin[\omega_k(t'-t)]$.

Appendix C : The explicit form of the matrices used in the TDDVR quantum and classical equations of motion

The explicit form of the matrices used in the quantum-classical equation of motion are presented as follows :

$$\bar{G}_{i_l, i_l'} = \frac{G_{i_l, i_l'}}{\sqrt{A_{i_l, i_l} A_{i_l', i_l'}}}, \quad \bar{F}_{i_l, i_l'} = \frac{F_{i_l, i_l'}}{\sqrt{A_{i_l, i_l} A_{i_l', i_l'}}},$$

$$d_{i_x i_y i_z i_r i_\theta i_\phi} = c_{i_x i_y i_z i_r i_\theta i_\phi} \prod_{l=1}^q (A_{i_l, i_l})^{\frac{1}{2}} \prod_{k=q}^p (A_{i_k, i_k})^{\frac{1}{2}},$$

$$A_{i_l, i_l'} = \sum_{n=0}^{N_l} \xi_n^*(x_{i_l}) \xi_n(x_{i_l'}), \quad A_{i_k, i_k'} = \sum_{n=0}^{N_k} \chi_n^*(X_{i_k}) \chi_n(X_{i_k'}),$$

$$G_{i_l, i_l'} = \sum_{n=0}^{N_l-1} \xi_{n+1}^*(x_{i_l}) \sqrt{n+1} \xi_n(x_{i_l'}) + \sum_{n=2}^{N_l} \xi_{n-1}^*(x_{i_l}) \sqrt{n} \xi_n(x_{i_l'}),$$

$$F_{i_l, i_l'} = \sum_{n=0}^{N_l-2} \xi_{n+2}^*(x_{i_l}) \sqrt{(n+1)(n+2)} \xi_n(x_{i_l'}) + \sum_{n=2}^{N_l} \xi_{n-2}^*(x_{i_l}) \sqrt{n(n-1)} \xi_n(x_{i_l'}) - \sum_{n=0}^{N_l} \xi_n^*(x_{i_l}) (2n-1) \xi_n(x_{i_l'}). \quad (\text{B1})$$

The TDDVR equation of motion for the quantum dynamics has the following important characteristics : (a) The component matrices ($\{\mathbf{A}_1\}$, $\{\mathbf{G}_1\}$, $\{\mathbf{F}_1\}$) of the TDDVR Hamiltonian matrix [see eq. (22)] are time-independent and need to be evaluated once for all; (b) Since the matrices, $\{\mathbf{G}_1\}$, are diagonal and associated with the ‘‘classical’’ variables $\{P_{X_l^c}(t)$, the non-linear dynamics of these ‘‘classical’’ quantities affects the convergence but not the final solution of the quantum equations of motion; (c) As the off-diagonal propagation of their associated parameters, $\{ImA_l\}$, is not desirable, and hence, a time-independent $\{ImA_l\}$ is the obvious choice.

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